

THE ROLE OF PROJECT METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract. *Teaching English at the university is a special responsibility associated not only with high-quality teaching of grammar and speaking, but also with learning how to use the language in a student's future career.*

It is always more difficult to teach the language of adults, because knowledge should be more applied and relevant. Thus, correctly selected methods of teaching English is the right strategy to achieve a high level of knowledge of students.

The main goal for a university teacher is to achieve, with the help of modern methods, a confident command of English by a student and its successful use in further professional activities.

Keywords: *teacher of English, teaching, applied sciences, quality education, teaching methods.*

Modern effective methods of teaching university students are:

- Interactive learning,
- Communicative methodology,
- Simulation of situations,
- Classical method,
- Text method.

Let's briefly consider the pros and cons of each method.

Interactive student learning

As a rule, people are divided into small groups, each of which is responsible for a certain part of the overall work or project. The main task of the teacher is to encourage students to interact with each other, the direction of the process and motivation.

During long-term interactive learning, the student learns:

- Building a dialogue, polylogue and maintaining contact with people,
- Exchange of information,
- Ability to work in a group, to be responsible for the overall result,
- The ability to put forward hypotheses and defend them in front of others,
- Ability to make non-standard decisions,
- Obtaining knowledge from the external environment,
- Effective time management.

Of the disadvantages, the following can be distinguished:

- Lack of personal study of the student's gaps,
- Secondary role of the teacher,
- Difficulties in the correct assessment of collective work.

Communicative methodology

The main goal is free interpersonal and intercultural communication of students in English both among themselves and with native speakers in future business relationships. Training is a constant communication of the teacher with students, discussion of materials, including audio and

video. As a result of learning by the communicative method , the student receives the following advantages ::

- Ability to build a dialogue with people in English,
- Familiarization with the culture of the language being studied,
- Memorizing and using situational cliches,
- Formation of an active professional vocabulary,
- Acquiring the skill of contacting other people to get information.

Despite the popularity of this technique in multi-level educational institutions, it has some drawbacks that should be taken into account by the teacher:

- Live communication does not involve deepening into grammar,
Some topics and expressions will be forgotten in the absence of language practice,
- In the process of communicative methodology, it is difficult to determine the personal abilities of students.

Modeling of communication situations in pairs of English

Three important components are used in this methodology: materials for external visibility (videos, photographs, objects), the student's imagination (the ability to imagine, predict, think out a situation, use their experience) and the ability to verbally express a thought, choose the necessary words and expressions.

Students learn to comment, form and express their point of view in this algorithm:

1. Familiarization with information,
2. Understanding the essence of the situation,
3. Applying your knowledge and experience to express the main idea,
4. Supplementing information with your point of view, evaluating information.

Advantages of this technique:

- With the right didactic material, the student receives practice-oriented knowledge.
- Along with studying English, students learn critical thinking and expressing their opinions.

The disadvantages of modeling situations are:

- Difficult to achieve consistency in learning.
- A large amount of time that is needed to listen and evaluate each person.

The classical method of language learning

The classical method includes consecutive classes in specialized literature.

An undeniable advantage can be called a clear, consistent language learning, starting with the grammatical basics, ending with the rules of using the language in everyday life. Among the significant disadvantages: the duration of training. As a rule, a thorough study of a foreign language takes about 3-5 years. For the success of this method , two components are needed:

- Determination and patience of the student,
- The same teacher who knows which topics have been learned and which have not.

Text method

The most commonly used method in domestic universities. Authentic texts are used as didactic materials, with which students work both at home and in pairs. In the process of working with texts, the professional thematic stock is replenished, the structure of writing texts is assimilated, the rules of writing words and grammatical constructions are studied. It should be

used either at the initial stages or at advanced ones as an analytical professional reading, but it is used everywhere in domestic universities

Disadvantages of the text method:

- Lack of speaking practice,
- The monotony of the material contributes to the loss of interest in the language,
- Ignoring other types of material limits the student's thinking.

There are several ways to improve the quality of language learning:

The diversity of the information space: the use of YouTube channels, podcasts, audiobooks, etc. for practicing pronunciation, updating vocabulary, analyzing global trends in the field under study.

Using computer technologies in the educational process: organization of joint lectures-conversations with students of another group/ university, online conferences, situational presentations, formation and joint discussion of case study, interactive projects.

Alternating techniques and a variety of activities in the classroom.

Constant self-education and honing of pedagogical skills.

Whichever method is chosen, the success of its application depends on the teacher. It is he who plays the main role in the correct, fast and high-quality education of both children and adults. Professionalism consists of a high level of English proficiency and a deep understanding of the theoretical and methodological basis of teaching.

Unfortunately, technologies are changing so fast that even the specialized pedagogical education received is not a guarantee of the quality of teaching, because any knowledge needs to be improved and refreshed. One of the most popular and effective ways to replenish knowledge is teacher certification.

The TEFL / TESOL certificate is a document that a person receives after completing online courses that study the theoretical and practical aspects of teaching English for children, adults, teenagers, as well as for lawyers, economists, private tutors and teachers in schools, colleges and universities. In addition, online classes include training in modern teaching methods: CLIL, ESP, online teaching.

Having received it, the teacher confirms his high qualification not only as an English speaker at a high level, but also as a teacher who owns popular teaching methods for students of different ages and levels.

The TEFL / TESOL certificate is an opportunity to obtain a work visa to China, Japan, Thailand, Israel, Brazil, Finland, France, Morocco, Greece, Czech Republic, Portugal, Italy, Poland, Australia, Great Britain, Singapore, Argentina, Spain, Bahrain, Dominican Republic, Germany, Hong Kong, Ireland, Mexico, Seychelles, Sri Lanka, Turkey.

REFERENCES

1. Korobova S.N. Increasing motivation in foreign language classes as part of the training of translators (English) Bulletin of the Moscow University. Series 22: Theory of Translation. 2012 No.2. pp.49-54.
2. Sample programs in foreign languages. The program of primary secondary education in French. The program of secondary (full) education in French. Basic level. The program of secondary (full) education in English. Profile level. Foreign languages at school. 2005. № 7.

3. Kuligina, A.V. Shchepilova. English. 7th GRADE book for teachers: a guide for teachers of general education institutions / A. S. Moscow, 2009. Ser. Your friend is English
4. E. Y. Grigorieva, E. Y. Gorbacheva, M. L. Lisenko English. Textbook of the French language for grades 10-11 of general education institutions /. Moscow, 2008. Ser. Moscow textbook (7th ed., ispr.)
5. A. S. Kuligina, M. G. Kiryanova. English. GRADE 2 textbook for general educational institutions with an application on electronic media / Moscow, 2011. Ser. Your friend is French (8th ed., dorab.)